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EFFECTS OF CONCEPT MAPPING STRATEGY ON READING SKILLS OF PUPILS WITH HARD OF HEARING IN JOS NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA PLATEAU STATE

Doris Yakubu Gomos ¹, Gang Musa Dachung ^{1*} & Alheri Alaku ²

¹ Department of Special Education and Rehabilitation Sciences,
University of Jos, Jos,
Plateau State

² Department of Educational Psychology,
FCT College of Education Zuba, Abuja

*Correspondence: dachungmusagang@gmail.com (GMD)

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Abstract: *This study investigated the effects of Concept Mapping Strategy on Reading Skills of Pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North, Plateau State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. This study is anchored on Orton Gillingham's Theory of Reading. The researcher adopted the non-equivalent quasi experimental research design. The population of this study consisted of twenty (20) primary three pupils with reading problems and hard of hearing in Jos North. Eight (8) primary three pupils with reading problems and hard of hearing in Jos North were selected as sample for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used in this study. The instrument that was used in this research for data collection; at both pre-test and post-test was Teacher Made Reading Skills Test. The data collected from the field were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study shows that Concept Mapping Strategy enhanced the spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing to a high extent. Concept Mapping Strategy enhances the word recognition of pupils with hard of hearing to a high extent. Furthermore, the study revealed that there is significant difference between post-test spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who were exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who were not. It is therefore recommended that pupils should be skilled in spelling and word recognition via concept mapping strategy. Teachers should be seriously trained or be made to learn how to apply concept mapping strategy in teaching children with hard of hearing*

Keywords: Mapping strategies, Reading skills, Hard of hearing, Plateau State, Nigeria

Introduction

Reading is defined in different ways by different scholars based on conception of the process of reading. Milaham (2019) defined reading as the interpretation of printed symbols. It is also a meaning gaining activity and a process of communication between the author and the reader. Furthermore, reading can be referred to as the ability to read texts with appropriate precision and expression. In order to read, the reader must be able to recognize letters of the alphabet and words at sight. The researcher feels that pupils with hard of hearing, need a reading programme that is different from the regular reading method obtain in most schools. Shaywitz (2003) opined that reading can be targeted through: repeated readings; echo readings; guided readings; self-identifying reading errors. And visualization. Reading skills can be taught through oral reading. And opportunities for feedback as the pupil reads. It is related largely to oral language proficiency.

Reading is the bedrock of all school subjects. Frequent failure in school by pupils with hard of hearing can be traced to inadequate reading skills. It is important to say that acquisition of reading can commonly be referred to as acquisition of knowledge foundation. Andzayi (2010) states that reading is built from three components: word recognition, spelling ability and literal comprehension. These three components once gained will then foster pupils with hard of hearing language competence, confidence and reading fluency.

The term impairment means different things to different persons; but it is worth saying and saying well that it is all about injury, wound or damage to body organ or structure. It refers to any abnormality or disorder of the structure or organ of the body; hard of hearing may simply be seen as an injury to an organ of hearing, thereby reducing the victim's ability to perceive sound according to societal norm. Word Recognition is purely taking a look at a written word and knowing, identifying or distinguishing the word at a glance. Word recognition skills enable pupils with hard of hearing to be aware of prints, recognize words and learn ways to consciously or unconsciously figure out and call out these words: that is unlock unknown words, perhaps by decoding the printed words and letters and by matching letters and words with or without sounds. Word recognition enables pupils with hard of hearing to concentrate on the meaning of the text. Word recognition skills could be taught such that it enables the reader to recognize words by sight without paying attention to the individual letters that make up the words. Andzayi and Umolu (2004) state that reading is built from three components: word recognition, spelling ability and literal comprehension. These three components once gained will then foster pupils with hard of hearing language competence, confidence and reading fluency. As pupils with hard of hearing grow in learning it is expected that their word recognition also develops and increase in number.

Jikukka (2018) opined that pupils with hard of hearing recognise and understand more words than they can say. By the age of three years, the average vocabulary of the normal pupil is about 900 words. Vocabulary continues to grow until the age of 6 and somewhat tends to move slowly. There is a sharp peak at 6 years. Jikukka (2018) further state that pupils with hard of hearing of primary three (3) ought to have mature language and good word recognition. At this stage he/she (pupil with hard of hearing) should involve syntax and reflection vocabulary of 5000 words plus. There is an increasingly high relationship between reading and word recognition, spelling ability and very significant literal comprehension. By repeated reading experiences pupils with hard of hearing develop word recognition and spelling ability of most words they see and read. This can only occur when: pupils with hard of hearing are provided multiple exposure words in a variety of reading contexts; words are taught in the context of a selection or unit: teachers help pupils with hard of hearing activate prior knowledge when

learning new words; relationships are drawn between new words and known words and concepts: pupils with hard of hearing are taught to use context clues and reference resources such as dictionaries to enhance their word recognition, and pupils with hard of hearing are encouraged to interact with the words so they are able to process them deeply and well recognized. Basically, there are three components of Reading which are, word recognition, spelling and literal comprehension.

Spelling ability is simply presenting letters of words through an already acquired knowledge of phonics sounds. Spelling is a set of conventions that regulate the way of using graphemes (writing system) to represent a language in its written form. Spelling is one of the elements of orthography. To spell is to show knowledge of the letters of a word in the correct order. Spelling ability is one of the scholastic skills that pupils with reading difficulties need to acquire in order to meet the common demands in classroom work at the primary school. Many primary three (3) pupils with reading difficulties in schools lack the capacity for spelling thereby retarding in their learning abilities and in classroom life generally. Dogo and Philemon (2017) said that a pupil with reading difficulties that is with limited spelling ability often suffer a great neglect from classmates, teachers and even parents or guardians. Eze (2007) averred that lack of spelling abilities often grossly affect pupil's academic performance and self-satisfaction. Reading skill is an educational dexterity, it is not an end in itself, but a means to an end.

Pupils with hard of hearing are those learners whose hearing has deviated from the societal hearing norm. Their hearing deviation does not hinder them from undergoing verbal reading training which is normally crucial for their holistic development, especially those of them that lack reading skills and as a result, are faced with technical hitches while reading. They modestly do have problems with spelling, word recognition and literal comprehension. Pupils with hard of hearing are usually unable to make meaning from read texts (Jikukka, 2018). From the researcher's simple experience as a teacher, it is needful to say that, it is rather unfortunate that many pupils with hard of hearing are without good reading skills. Pupils with hard of hearing habitually finish pre-primary school without basic reading skills required for mastery of spelling, word recognition and literal comprehension which are prerequisite for acquisition of knowledge, self-development and basic reading skills that are fundamental for proficient education and studies at the various stages in primary school and beyond.

For most pupils with hard of hearing who have problem with reading skills, early intervention training through concept mapping strategy is ideal. This training often combines instruction on reading skills (such as spelling, word recognition and literal comprehension) for the edification and personal development of these pupils with hard of hearing. Once it is provided by well-trained teachers, it can change the pupils with hard of hearing to become excellent in reading.

Concept mapping strategy is a systematic and organized training achievable after phonic sounds of letters; it is a logical and well-thought-out training towards the acquisition of reading skills through phonics sounds, amongst primary school pupils with hard of hearing. The regular reading movement in English Language is done from left hand to right hand and it is done horizontally. But concept mapping strategy reading and especially word recognition is done by blending phonic sounds (sounds of letters); it is precise, logical, methodical and structured in such a way that reading skills and its concepts involve movement in rows and columns; from simple to complex. Movements while calling or reading words are from left-to-right (forward/horizontally), top-to-bottom (downward/vertically) Bottom-to-top (upward) and all those are in rows and columns.

Related calisthenics movements and maneuvers are also done for the phonic sounds of the other vowels: e, i, o, u. Intensive drills normally characterize Concept mapping strategy trainings as it is

commonly obtained in military exercises or cardiovascular exercises; frequently carried out in straight line, up and down or in rows and columns. Concept mapping strategy is a meticulous and prearranged technique of instilling reading skills into pupils with hard of hearing.

Strydom (2008) and Loong and Aziz (2019) emphasized that the main objective of concept mapping strategy is to practice, perfect and automatize the skills that underlie reading. It is both a treatment and rehabilitation plan which is time-limited, structure based on academic considerations and phonics of letters strategies. It is both a counseling and a social-therapy programme, which consists of Reading-Therapy Tips (RTT), Reading Skills Games (RSG): Puzzles, Brainteasers and plenary or discussion sessions. Concept mapping strategy is very useful in teaching phonics, blending phonic sounds and learning reading processes; it enhances and improves word recognition, spelling abilities and literal comprehension of pupils with hard of hearing, Deshi (2018) illustrated that it is a training that was originally designed to help pupils with hard of hearing solve reading skills problems through phonics sounds, common sense and reasoning.

Primary three (3) is one of the most important and crucial stages for acquisition of reading skills. Primary three level is that imperative platform for basic reading to be inculcated into pupils with hard of hearing. From the researcher's experience as a teacher, many pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North LGA are pupils with reading difficulty (spelling, comprehension and word recognition) difficulties: it is those that necessitated the use of concept mapping strategy in this investigation. To a great extent, the researcher feels that primary schools are places where reading can be impacted or achieved, and pupils with hard of hearing can best be helped to become graceful readers. It is in the light of the above that the researcher finds it very necessary to investigate the Effects of Concept Mapping Strategy on Reading Skills of Pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North, Plateau State.

Statement of the Problem

Reading and especially, literal comprehension is often a difficult task for pupils with hard of hearing in over populated classrooms, yet over populated classes are synonymous with many classrooms in Jos North LGA; large class sizes do not give room for effective reading comprehension exercise. For many pupils with hard of hearing, they are troubled for the noise that goes with large class size and are also worried for such an atmosphere, besides the problems that go with it: class size utterly needs to be controlled if literal comprehension must be encouraged or aided. Pupils with reading difficulties neither comprehend reading text books instructions nor express themselves satisfactorily or write down their thoughts: if they do, it is either poor or disappointing. Numerous pupils with hard of hearing lack literal comprehension abilities or essential trainings for developing literal comprehension. Part of the problem is that many persons and even teachers often feel and think that literal comprehension is gained naturally, but it is not (Andreason, 2015).

The negatives ways and teething troubles of reading difficulties are always obvious in class tasks, learning and self-expressions of pupils with hard of hearing. Theses pupils most often than not cannot express themselves satisfactorily. Pupils with hard of hearing lack inspiring reading essentials for developing proper reading skills. This often amount to uncertainties and hesitations to both the pupil with hard of hearing and the teacher who is the instructor.

While reading is considered to be a basic need in the modern world of science and technology, many primary three pupils with hard of hearing in a lot of schools lack reading skills. Some pupils with hard of hearing had dropped out of schools due to reading difficulties and without acquiring the necessary spelling comprehension and word recognition skills; more so, many of these pupils with hard

of hearing read without achieving high as readers do.

There has not been schools or training centers that are ready and willing to impart basic Spelling, literal comprehension and word recognition abilities into pupils with hard of hearing, as a result so many pupils with hard of hearing had dropped out of school prematurely. Even though Government had many reading trainings in Jos North LGA and Plateau State at large but still these pupils with hard of hearing are not able to read to the optimal.

The researcher feels that many parents and guardians have never obtain reading skills nor known the importance of reading skills, as such, never enroll their pupils with hard of hearing for reading programmes such as concept mapping strategy that have direct bearing with reading skills acquisition. Acquisition of reading skills is never regarded by many parents and in some cases teachers, to be of any importance or significance, nor to enrich the quality of lives of pupils with hard of hearing. Part of the problem here is that some parents and guardians have never see the need to get their pupils with hard of hearing engaged in any reading training let alone concept mapping strategy to change their reading difficulties or improve the state of their reading.

Reading of many primary school pupils with hard of hearing are nothing to write home about. Pupils with hard of hearing struggle with reading for a variety of reasons including limited experience with phonetics awareness and absence of preliminary reading books and reading materials, as a result, they find it difficult to organize text information, comprehend texts and also find it difficult to organize reading related ideas.

As a teacher over the years in Jos North LGA, it is observed that poor reading abilities are related to a higher incident of frustration, delinquency, criminality and law-breaking. Adding to the urgency of this situation is the fact that, without typical instruction, some pupils with hard of hearing at the primary school level shall remain weak in reading skills as they are pupils with hard of hearing in schools.

Teachers are not finding it easy to teach reading skills in primary schools and especially: teaching phonics, learning through blending of phonics sounds which are effective ways to teaching emergent readers. In addition, early difficulties with basic reading skills, characteristically result in limited time engagement in text reading and because of this lack of exposure to text, decoding problem eventually becomes a generalized deficit and comprehension is grossly affected, thereby contributing to the teething reading troubles of the pupil with hard of hearing.

Therefore, preparing pupils with hard of hearing adequately for reading expertise should be seen as an essential part of the pupil's education. This study therefore is centered principally on the effects of concept mapping strategy on reading skills of pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to find out the effects of concept mapping strategy on reading skills of pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North, Plateau State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Find out the effect of concept mapping strategy on spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing.
2. Ascertain the effects of concept mapping strategy on the word recognition of pupils with hard of hearing.

Research Questions

The following questions are posed for investigation:

1. What is the effect of concept mapping strategy on spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing after exposure to concept mapping strategy?
2. What is the effect of concept mapping strategy on the word recognition of pupils with hard of hearing?

Hypotheses

The following Hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 Level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing between those who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who were not.
2. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test word recognition mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing between those who are exposed to treatment and those who were not.

Methodology

The study is experimental research. The researcher adopted the non-equivalent quasi experimental research design. The choice of this design is due to the fact that the nature of the study requires determining the effect of treatment on pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North LGA (the study area). This design also provides opportunity for the researcher to determine how the independent variable interact to influence the dependent variable.

Quasi experimental design could be used in such situation. The non-equivalent control group design can be illustrated as shown below:

Groups	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
Experimental	O ₁	X	O ₂
Control	O ₃	–	O ₄

O₁ = Pre-test for Experimental Group

X = Treatment

O₂ = Post-test for Experimental Group

O₃ = Pre-test for Control Group

– = Absence of Treatment

O₄ = Post-test for Control Group

The population of this study consisted of twenty (20) primary three pupils with reading problems and hard of hearing in Otana Integrated School Jos North LGA Plateau State. For the purpose of this investigation, one arm of the three arms of primary three was assigned as the experimental group with four (4) pupils, while the second randomly chosen arm was assigned as the control group with four (4) pupils. This gives the total of eight (8) pupils as the total sample. The sampling technique in this research was the Non-Probability Technique and the type of Non-Probability Technique was the purposive sampling. The instrument that was used in this research for data collection; at both pre-test and post-test was Teacher Made Reading Skills Test (TMRST).

Teacher Made Reading Skills Test was used in this research for data collection at pre-test and post-test. The Teacher Made Reading Skills Test (TMRST) was in two parts. Part A. elicit information from the respondents about their personal data such as: designation, class and any other important information. Part B. measure the respondents' spelling ability, word recognition and reading level.

The data collected from the field was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The data collected for the study research questions were answer using the mean and standard deviation while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed in testing hypotheses 1 to 2. The data were analysed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.

Results

Research Question One

What is the effect of concept mapping strategy on spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing after exposure to concept mapping strategy?

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of Spelling Ability of Pupils with Hard of Hearing After Exposure to Concept Mapping Strategy

Groups	N	Pretest Mean	Standard Deviation	Post-test Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Gain	Post-test Mean Difference
Experimental	4	4.50	1.00	13.50	2.65	9.00	6.75
Control	4	3.75	.96	6.75	.96	3.00	

Table 1 shows the pretest and posttest spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing in the Experimental and Control Groups. The pupils with hard of hearing in experimental group had a pretest mean scores of 4.50 and a posttest mean scores of 13.50 with mean gain of 9.00, while pupils with hard of hearing in control group had a pretest mean scores of 3.75 and a posttest mean scores of 6.75 with a mean gain score of 3.00. This implies that Concept Mapping Strategy enhances the spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing high extent than pupils with hard of hearing in the control group.

Research Question Two

What is the effect of concept mapping strategy on the word recognition of pupils with hard of hearing?

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of Word Recognition of Pupils with Hard of Hearing After Exposure to Concept Mapping Strategy

Groups	N	Pretest Mean	Standard Deviation	Post-test Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Gain	Post-test Mean Difference
Experimental	4	4.50	1.29	14.75	3.20	10.25	7.25
Control	4	4.25	1.26	7.50	.58	3.25	

Table 2 shows the pretest and posttest word recognition mean scores of the pupils with hard of hearing in Experimental and Control Groups. The pupils with hard of hearing in the experimental group had a pretest mean scores of 4.50 and posttest mean scores of 14.75 with mean gain of 10.25, while pupils

with hard of hearing in control group had a pretest mean scores of 4.25 and a posttest mean scores of 7.50 with a mean gain score of 3.25. This implies that Concept Mapping Strategy enhances the word recognition of pupils with hard of hearing to a high extent than pupils with hard of hearing in the control group.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of Spelling Ability of Pupils with Hard of Hearing After Exposure to Concept Mapping Strategy

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	Pretest	1.125 ^a	1	1.125	1.174	.320	.164
	Posttest	91.125 ^b	1	91.125	23.021	.003	.793
Intercept	Pretest	136.125	1	136.125	142.043	.000	.959
	Posttest	820.125	1	820.125	207.189	.000	.972
GROUPS	Pretest	1.125	1	1.125	1.174	.320	.164
	Posttest	91.125	1	91.125	23.021	.003	.793
Error	Pretest	5.750	6	.958			
	Posttest	23.750	6	3.958			
Total	Pretest	143.000	8				
	Posttest	935.000	8				
Corrected Total	Pretest	6.875	7				
	Posttest	114.875	7				

a. R Squared = .164 (Adjusted R Squared = .024)

b. R Squared = .793 (Adjusted R Squared = .759)

Table 3 shows the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on pretest and posttest mean scores of spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing after exposure to concept mapping strategy. Before intervention, $F_{1,6} = 1.174$ and p-value of 0.320, since the p-value is less than 0.05. Therefore, there is significant difference between pre-test spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

In addition, after intervention, $F_{1,6} = 23.021$ and p-value of 0.003. Therefore, there is significant difference between post-test spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test word recognition mean scores of pupils

with hard of hearing who are exposed to treatment and those who are not.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores of Word Recognition of Pupils with Hard of Hearing After Exposure to Concept Mapping Strategy

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	Pretest	.125 ^a	1	.125	.077	.791	.013
	Posttest	105.125 ^b	1	105.125	19.866	.004	.768
Intercept	Pretest	153.125	1	153.125	94.231	.000	.940
	Posttest	990.125	1	990.125	187.110	.000	.969
GROUPS	Pretest	.125	1	.125	.077	.791	.013
	Posttest	105.125	1	105.125	19.866	.004	.768
Error	Pretest	9.750	6	1.625			
	Posttest	31.750	6	5.292			
Total	Pretest	163.000	8				
	Posttest	1127.000	8				
Corrected Total	Pretest	9.875	7				
	Posttest	136.875	7				

a. R Squared = .013 (Adjusted R Squared = -.152)

b. R Squared = .768 (Adjusted R Squared = .729)

Table 4 shows the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on pretest and posttest mean scores of Word Recognition of pupils with hard of hearing after exposure to concept mapping strategy. Before intervention, $F_{1,6} = .077$ and p-value of 0.791. Therefore, there is significant difference between pretest Word Recognition mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

In addition, after intervention, $F_{1,6} = 19.866$ and p-value of 0.004. Therefore, there is significant difference between post-test Word Recognition mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

Discussion

The study on effects of concept mapping strategy on reading skills of pupils with hard of hearing in Jos North Local Government Area, Nigeria. The findings of Research Question One in Table 1 show the pretest and posttest spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing in the Experimental and Control Groups. The pupils with hard of hearing in experimental group had a pretest mean scores of 4.50 and a posttest mean scores of 13.50 with mean gain of 9.00, while pupils with hard of hearing in control group had a pretest mean scores of 3.75 and a posttest mean scores of 6.75 with a mean gain score of 3.00. This implies that Concept Mapping Strategy enhances the spelling ability of pupils with hard of hearing high extent than pupils with hard of hearing in the control group.

Table 2 shows the pretest and posttest word recognition mean scores of the pupils with hard of hearing

in Experimental and Control Groups. The pupils with hard of hearing in the experimental group had a pretest mean scores of 4.50 and posttest mean scores of 14.75 with mean gain of 10.25, while pupils with hard of hearing in control group had a pretest mean scores of 4.25 and a posttest mean scores of 7.50 with a mean gain score of 3.25. This implies that Concept Mapping Strategy enhances the word recognition of pupils with hard of hearing to a high extent than pupils with hard of hearing in the control group.

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In addition, after intervention, $F_{1,6} = 23.021$ and p-value of 0.003. Therefore, there is significant difference between post-test spelling ability mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

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In addition, after intervention, $F_{1,6} = 19.866$ and p-value of 0.004. Therefore, there is significant difference between post-test Word Recognition mean scores of pupils with hard of hearing who are exposed to concept mapping strategy and those who are not.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter synthesizes the study's results, offering insights into the effects of concept mapping strategy on reading skills of pupils with hard of hearing. The positive outcomes underscore the potential of collaborative and tailored interventions in improving reading skills amongst this population. The implications for practice and recommendations for future research contribute to the broader discourse on educational practices for pupils with hard of hearing and continuous research on alternative ways to improve hard of hearing pupils reading skills.

Recommendations

The suggestion that the research suggests for pupils with hard of hearing and teachers are: pupils should be skilled in spelling, word recognition and literal comprehension via concept mapping strategy. Teachers should be seriously trained or be made to learn and how to apply treatment such as concept mapping strategy on reading skills as well as teachers should seek for ways to improve hard of hearing pupils reading problems. Future researches may include the use of findings for practice in learning process and the needs for further researches regarding to factors in reading abilities or skills.

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